

D6.1 Visual Identity & Project Website

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Executive summary

This deliverable explains how Eurecat, responsible of the SubTask 6.1.1. “Visual Identity and Website” has developed VitiGEOSS’s Visual Corporative Image (VCI) and project webpage. The document includes the project’s logo, Word templates for project activities, a Power Point template for presentations and a visual identity standards guidebook defining and outlining how to use identifying elements pertaining to VitiGEOSS, such as logos, colours, fonts and graphic elements.

In addition, this deliverable also describes how the VitiGEOSS’s project webpage has been created, summarising the structure, the content and some functionalities of the website.

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List of abbreviations

<i>EU</i>	<i>European Union</i>
<i>EO</i>	<i>Earth Observation</i>
<i>WP</i>	<i>Work Package</i>
<i>VCI</i>	<i>Visual Corporate Image</i>

Introduction

VitiGEOSS is a 3-year and a half project aiming to promote the use of European open Earth observation (EO) services, developing an **innovative vineyard management tool based on the integration of EO and in-field sensors** to increase resolutions and reliability of satellite information applied to viticulture sector.

The project also has the objective to respond to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which requires to **intensify the production in a sustainable way, mitigating the effects of climate change, reducing negative environmental externalities and promoting local economic growth.**

Eurecat is the partner leader of the **SubTask 6.1.1. Visual Identity and Website (M01-M03)**, which has the purpose to design and provide a coherent and recognizable corporate visual image to be used in all project communication materials. In addition, this task aims to develop the VitiGEOSS's website which will contain general information on the project, the main outputs, public reports and scientific publications, news, events attended by the partners and dissemination materials.

This document presents the visual identity materials designed, including a logo, a presentation template, Word templates and a visual identity manual to be implemented in all communication and dissemination project activities. On the other hand, the document also explains how VitiGEOSS project webpage has been created and all issues that have been taken into consideration. This deliverable summarises the structure, the content and the functionalities of the website developed in the scope of the project, as well as the data protection measures adopted within the site.

Project's Corporate Visual Identity

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing VitiGEOSS official Visual Corporate Image (VCI), aimed at properly aligning all communication and dissemination materials across all the tasks of the project.

The Visual Corporate Image is crucial to create and establish VitiGEOSS's identity, as well as to give a coherent and consistent image of the project. **It is also important to use the elements established in the VCI manual properly and only employ the authorised documents templates in order to convey the properties and goals of the project as a brand and do it consistently.**

The following sections describe the different materials and elements designed, including the VitiGEOSS project's logo, templates, colours, fonts and graphic elements to be used in all communication and dissemination actions by all project's partners.

1. VitiGEOSS logo

The logo is the main brand element of the visual identity of VitiGEOSS and has the purpose to represent the different concepts surrounding the project.

As pictured in Figure 1, VitiGEOSS's logo **symbolises grape on a vine representing the main sector in which the innovation developed by the project will be applied.** Additionally, the logo also includes an icon of the earth and a satellite, symbolising two of the project's topics, concretely Earth Observation (EO) and satellite imagery services. The logo designed includes the **two main colours of the project and the acronym with the special font used for some materials and established in the project's visual identity manual.**

Figure 1: VitiGEOSS full colour logo

Depending on its application, different versions of the logo have been developed, including an all-black version (Figure 2) to be used whenever the full colour logo cannot be used, a specific version for social media and profile pictures (Figure 3), and a white version (Figure 4) of its use when applied in front of a colour background.

Figure 2: black and white logo

Figure 3: Full colour logo avatar to be used on social media and profile pictures

Figure 4: Logo adaptation on a green and purple corporate colour

Several examples on how to use the logo are included in the visual corporate identity manual in order to guide partners during its application in project materials.

Figure 5: Logo adaptation on a background with an image

2. Visual Corporate Identity (VCI) manual

A visual identity and standards manual has been created and distributed among all partners to ensure that project's branding is not compromised, and all partners are capable to use the elements properly with the objective to convey the properties and goals of the VitiGEOSS project as a brand.

The visual identity guidelines define and outline how to use identifying elements pertaining to the project, including logos, fonts, colours, stationery and graphic resources. Additionally, it sets a design layout for project promotional materials to be developed in the next months. Partners should treat and use this manual as a source of the materials and instructions and as a basis for further development of project materials.

The sections hereinafter include and describe some parts designed in the manual:

2.1 Corporate colours

This section presents the project's colour palette that must be used in all project's materials, such as the website, social media and other promotional and graphic elements.

According to the palette designed, the main colour of VitiGEOSS is **purple Merlot (#EB6025)**, while **green Macabeu (#9abf1d)** and **black Cep (#000000)** will be the complementary colours of the project. It is important to mention that the colours and their names have also been created to refer the main colours of grape, vineyards and grapevines.

Figure 6: VitiGEOSS colours palette

2.2 Fonts

The VCI manual also establishes **three types of fonts to be used for project documents and materials.**

“**BARLOW CONDENSED MEDIUM**” will be the special font used for titles of promotional and advertising materials. This type of font and its different versions are free, and partners can download it from Google Fonts.

Download the “Barlow condensed medium” font [here](#)

As the manual establishes, the text font for promotional and communication items will be “**Titillium Web Regular**”, which can be also downloaded in Google Fonts Page for free [here](#).

On the other hand, according to the manual, “**Trebuchet MS**” is the **main font established for deliverables and internal documents** because it is a standard Microsoft Office font included in Word and Power Point documents, among some others. The use of this font will be explained in more detail in sections hereinafter.

Figure 7: Fonts for promotional and communication issues

Figure 8: VitiGEOSS fonts for deliverables and other internal documents

2.3 Stationery

The Visual Corporative Identity manual designed for VitiGEOSS project also includes different elements designed for stationery materials, such as letters, envelopes, business cards, the image of the project for digital supports and applications and other internal and external documents that partners may use every time they need.

Figure 9: VitiGEOSS stationery

2.4 Graphic resources

This section shows the graphic items which can be used for the design of promotional materials, externals and internal project presentations or other documents. **These elements have been broadly used for the design of the project's Word and Power Point templates, as well as headers for the project's Twitter account.**

Figure 10: Graphic resources to be used for designing VitiGEOSS's materials

2.5 Twitter header

The Visual Corporate Identity guidebook also includes a Twitter header template which has been already used and integrated in the project’s account.

Figure 11: Two versions of Twitter headers templates

Figure 12: VitiGE OSS Twitter page with the header designed

2.6 Promotional materials layout

Different templates for promotional and advertising materials have been created to be used for the design of flyers, rollups and totems.

The VCI manual includes design proposals for project's communication and marketing materials, such as a rollup, posters and the brochure, which will be created in the following months.

Figure 13: Flyer template

Figure 14: Rollup templates (two versions)

3. Templates

Eurecat has prepared different templates, which have been already shared with all partners. A Power Point template has been created for internal and external presentations, as well as three different Word documents: one for deliverables, one for meetings’ agenda and other purposes and another one to be used for meetings’ minutes.

These template materials must be used throughout all project’s execution in order to maintain a coherent and consistent image.

3.1 Power Point presentation template

A Power Point template has been designed to be used for all VitiGEOSS project’s internal and external presentations.

This document includes a variety of slides with different options to include the text and different visual elements and to be used and adapted by all partners when preparing an internal or external project’s presentation.

A screenshot of some slides is shown below:

Figure 15: Slides of VitiGEOSS Power Point presentation template

3.2 Template for deliverables

A Word document template has been produced and shared with all the consortium partners to be used for all project's deliverables.

This template establishes the use of a page header with the project's logo and the funding body's logo and a footer with some information about the document and a graphic element created for project materials.

Aspects related the fonts used, size, tables, figures, ordered and unordered lists, references, footnotes, etc. are defined in the template.

Figure 16: View of some pages of the deliverable template

3.3 Template for agenda

The template designed for the agenda presents a header page with the VitiGEOSS and funding body's logo and a footer with some information of the project. The font used for title agenda's document is Trebuchet MS 16pt Bold and in the main project corporate colour and for the normal text is also Trebuchet MS 10pt, single line spacing and justified.

A screenshot of the template is shown below:

The image shows a screenshot of a meeting agenda template. At the top left is the VitiGEOSS logo, and at the top right is the European Union flag. The main title is 'AGENDA MEETING'. Below it, there are fields for 'Date: XX/XX/XXXX' and 'Venue: Eureka'. The core of the template is a table with three columns: 'Time', 'Topic', and 'Presenter/Facilitator'. The table contains several rows for different parts of the meeting, including 'Welcome and Introductions', 'WP1', 'WP2', 'Coffee Break', 'WP3', 'Lunch', 'WP4, WP5, WP6', and 'Evening meal'. Below the table, there are sections for 'Resources:', 'Special notes and information:', and 'Venue' with sub-points for 'Accommodation' and 'Transportation'. At the bottom left, there is a decorative border of asterisks and the text 'VitiGEOSS Agenda Template'. At the bottom right, it says 'Page 1 of 1'.

Time	Topic	Presenter/Facilitator
09:30 - 09:45	Welcome and Introductions	EUT
09:45 - 10:30	WP1	EUT
10:30 - 11:15	WP2	
11:15 - 11:45	Coffee Break	
11:45 - 13:15	WP3	EUT
13:15 - 14:45	Lunch	
14:45 - 15:45	WP4, WP5, WP6	EUT
19:00	Evening meal	All

Figure 17: VitiGEOSS agenda template

3.4 Template for minutes

This template will be used for taking minutes of project meetings and recording the list of attendants. This document also includes a header page with the VitiGEOSS logo and reference to the EU funding and a footer with some information.

For the main title of the document **Trebuchet MS 16pt Bold** is used in the main project corporate colour, while for subsections headings the font used is **Trebuchet MS 14pt** and for normal text **Trebuchet MS 11pt**.

See below some screenshots of this template:

Figure 18: Word template for minutes

Project website

According to the work plan, Eurecat is responsible for designing and implementing the official VitiGEOSS project website. The registered URL is www.vitigeoss.eu.

The sections hereinafter describe the web platform. The website will be the anchor for all communication activities related to the project and will serve as a central point of entry for all public material, including the project's basic information, expected impacts and objectives. The website will be continuously updated with news, links to other relevant sites, details of published papers, conferences and exhibitions during the project and will remain active at least during three years after the project's finalization to support the exploitation of project outputs.

The website platform follows the corporate visual identity of the project and it gives access to VitiGEOSS social media channels (Twitter so far).

Considering that different authors might update the site, a Content Management System (CMS) has been adopted, to easily and quickly publish the content. Eurecat proposes to use Wordpress, as the Eurecat's Research Communications Office has wide experience with this CMS.

Regarding the website languages, the basis is English but if a need to translate some parts of the website arise, a multilingual plugin will be installed for this purpose.

It is essential that the website is optimised for browsing on tablets and smart phones, so the website has been developed using a responsive design approach.

1. Website structure

The following information architecture for VitiGEOSS website is proposed in the figure below. In purple, you can see the pages /structure that have been created for the website launch, while, in green, the pages that will be developed afterwards, in line with project advances.

Further changes to the website structure may be made in the future to allocate documents and dissemination actions, as well as to support specific WP or tasks.

2. Website content

The texts hereinafter describe the contents published on the first version of the website.

2.1 Homepage

It includes one sliders: *“Vineyard innovative tools based on the integration of Earth Observation services and in-field sensors”*.

The homepage also includes a short description of the project, its main objectives and key outputs, as well as a section on the context.

In addition, a section mentioning the consortium linking to the partners page has been designed and included in the homepage.

As soon as the “News & Events” sections have some new articles and contents, a section at the homepage showing the latest publications, together with the project’s twitter feed will be created. Specific sections will be created to promote and divulge the platform and information services that will be created during the project. Specific sections will be created to promote and divulge the platform and information services that will be created during the project.

VitiGEOSS in a nutshell

A single-entry point solution for wine producers aiming to boost vineyards sustainability

VitiGEOSS project integrates and improves existing solutions coupling satellite imagery with in-field sensors to **increase resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to all aspects of viticulture and specific wine-business operations.**

The main scope of the project is to **make use of the potential of European Earth Observation initiatives** for deploying an **innovative commercial information solution** to optimise sustainable grapevine cultivation via **decision support systems (DSS) on phenology, irrigation, fertilisation, disease and business and sustainability management.**

BUTTON- FIND OUT MORE - link to “About VitiGEOSS”

Key outcomes

Weather and climate forecasts

Phenological monitoring

Crop status monitoring

Disease management

Business and sustainability management

BUTTON - FIND OUT MORE - LINK TO SOLUTION PAGE

VitiGEOSS AMBITION

VitiGEOSS goal is to contribute to a responsible production of wine by minimising the use of chemical fertilisers and pesticides and offering tools for a better management and optimisation of resources for greater sustainability

Pilots

VitiGEOSS solution will be validated in three vineyards of top European wine producers in Italy, Spain and Portugal.

BUTTON - FIND OUT MORE - LINK TO PILOTS PAGE

News & Events

This section will include a Twitter widget and will show the latest news and events published on the website.

Our team

VitiGEOSS interdisciplinary consortium is made up of 9 partners from 4 European countries. 4 research institutions, 2 technological companies and 3 wine producers.

LOGOS PARTNERS

BUTTON - KNOW THE WHOLE CONSORTIUM - Link to the “Consortium” page

Vineyard innovative tools based on the integration of Earth Observation services and in-field sensors

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

VitiGE OSS in a nutshell

A single-entry point solution for wine producers aiming to boost vineyards sustainability

VitiGE OSS project integrates and improves existing solutions coupling satellite imagery with in-field sensors to increase resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to all aspects of viticulture and specific wine-business operations.

The main scope of the project is to make use of the potential of European Earth Observation initiatives for deploying an innovative commercial information solution to optimise sustainable grapevine cultivation via decision support systems (DSS) on phenology, irrigation, fertilisation, disease and business and sustainability management.

[> FIND OUT MORE](#)

Key outputs

- » Weather and climate forecasts
- » Phenological monitoring
- » Crop status monitoring
- » Disease management
- » Business and sustainability management

VitiGE OSS goal is to contribute to a responsible production of wine by minimising the use of chemical fertilisers and pesticides and offering tools for a better management and optimisation of resources for greater sustainability

María Navarro, Project Coordinator, Eurecat

CONTACT US!

Pilots

VitiGE OSS solution will be validated in three vineyards of top European wine producers in Italy, Spain and Portugal.

The vineyards from the end users will be used for the calibration and validation of the project's services.

[> FIND OUT MORE](#)

Our team

VITIGE OSS interdisciplinary consortium is made up of **9 partners** from **4 European countries**. **4** research institutions, **2** technological companies and **3** wine producers.

Eurecat

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

eLEAF

Familia Torres

Price Waterhouse Coopers – PwC

Symington Family Estates

Fondazione LINKS

Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II

Mastroberardino Società Agricola srl

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VITIGE OSS Retweeted

INEA @inea_eu

Did you know that #MachineLearning & High Performance Computing #HPC can be used to prevent & control #grape vine diseases?

Check out how the #CEFTelecom project @grapevine_pro is doing it resulting in higher quality & safer products

[grapevine-project.eu](#) #EU #OpenData

4h

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Manage cons...

Figure 19: View of VitiGE OSS homepage

2.2 About VitiGEOSS

2.2.1 VitiGEOSS project

This section includes the main information about the project, the main objectives and the expected impact. The content of the page is organised in the following sub-sections:

The project

Providing forecasts, estimations and recommendations to wine makers to optimise vineyard management processes

The VitiGEOSS project aims to **use of European Open Earth Observation services** for the improvement of agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental and local level.

To do so, the project will develop an **innovative vineyard management solution [LINK TO SOLUTION]** based on the integration of Earth Observation services and in-field sensors with the objective to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to the viticulture sector.

The innovative solution promoted by the project has the objective to respond to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which requires to **intensify the production in a sustainable way, mitigate the effects of climate change, reduce negative environmental externalities and promote local economic growth.**

Start date - 1 September 2020. End date - 28 February 2024 (42 months)

Objectives

- [ICON] Deploy a **weather/climate forecast intelligent service** to provide a robust forecast for decision making processes in the wine sector.
- [ICON] Deploy a **disease management system capable of launching warning alerts on the appearance of the most important diseases** based on the symptoms and characteristics of each geographical area.
- [ICON] Build a **set of Copernicus and EOSS downstream services** integrating satellite information with in-situ data to optimise the crop management using the highest quality data.
- [ICON] Establish an **integrated, modular management solution for vineyard cultivation in three demo-sites** using Earth Observation systems and field monitoring tools.
- [ICON] **Validation of sustainable wine production indicators** to empower decision makers in the wine sector with the necessary toolbox to make wine production sustainable.
- [ICON] Develop a **successful market entry strategy**, based on market analysis and stakeholder consultation.
- [ICON] **Build capacity among technology developers and commercialization partners** to ensure the usability of project results.

Concept

Pilot demonstrators

The solution of VitiGEOSS will be proven in **three demo sites** in Spain, Italy and Portugal, in which will be devoted a pilot vineyard for the project.

During the first year, those vineyards will be used for the calibration of all services and in the second and third year, the services will be tested, validated and deviations analysed for possible further corrections

BUTTON - MORE INFORMATION - link to pilots page

WPs

WP1 - Project management

Overall management of the activities to be performed in the project, including administration and financial affairs, quality assurance, risk management, data management and innovation management.

WP2 - Intelligent services or vineyard management

Design and operationally deliver a set of Intelligent Services (ISs) aimed to feed the VitiGEOSS platform to promote a more effective vineyard management and decision support.

WP3 - Integrated Vineyard Management Application Portal (DSS)

Deployment of the VitiGEOSS cloud-based application portal providing a one-stop-shop for viticultural applications to end-users.

WP4 - Demonstration

Validation of the in-field performances of VitiGEOSS platform and information services in supporting viticulturists to manage the vineyard based on sustainability indicators.

WP5 - Commercial innovation and market penetration

Evaluation of the future sustainability of VitiGEOSS and analyses market critical policies and financial constraints required to promote the sustainable wine growing approach using the sustainability checker application provided in WP2.

WP6 - Communication and Dissemination

Planning and development of communication and dissemination activities to facilitate knowledge transfer to end users, spread the use of Earth Observation services and climate services among the agriculture sector and promote the market uptake of VitiGEOSS solutions.

The project

Providing forecasts, estimations and recommendations to wine makers to optimise vineyard management processes

The VitiGEOSS project aims to use of **European Open Earth Observation services** for the improvement of agriculture business operations at an economic, environmental and local level.

To do so, the project will develop an **Innovative vineyard management solution** based on the integration of Earth Observation services and in-field sensors with the objective to increase the resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to the viticulture sector.

The innovative solution promoted by the project has the objective to respond to future challenges of the worldwide food and wine industry, which requires to **Intensify the production in a sustainable way, mitigate the effects of climate change, reduce negative environmental externalities and promote local economic growth.**

Start date – 1 September 2020

End date – 28 February 2024 (42 months)

Objectives

- Weather & climate forecast**
 Deploy a **weather/climate forecast intelligent service** to provide a robust forecast for decision making processes in the wine sector.
- Sustainable wine production**
 Validation of **sustainable wine production indicators** to empower decision makers in the wine sector with the necessary toolbox to make wine production sustainable.
- Disease management system**
 Deploy a **disease management system capable of launching warning alerts on the appearance of the most important diseases** based on the symptoms and characteristics of each geographical area.
- Market strategy**
 Develop a **successful market entry strategy**, based on market analysis and stakeholder consultation.
- EOSS downstream services**
 Build a set of **Copernicus and EOSS downstream services** integrating satellite information with in-situ data to optimise the crop management using the highest quality data.
- Commercialisation**
 Build **capacity among technology developers and commercialisation partners** to ensure the usability of project results.
- Management solution**
 Establish an **integrated, modular management solution for vineyard cultivation in three demo-sites** using Earth Observation systems and field monitoring tools.

Pilot demonstrators

The solution of VitiGEOSS will be proven in **three demo sites** in Spain, Italy and Portugal, in which will be devoted a pilot vineyard for the project.

During the first year, those vineyards will be used for the calibration of all services and in the second and third year, the services will be tested, validated and deviations analysed for possible further corrections.

[FIND OUT MORE](#)

Work Packages

WP1	WP2	WP3	WP4	WP5	WP6
-----	-----	-----	-----	-----	-----

Project management

Overall management of the activities to be performed in the project, including administration and financial affairs, quality assurance, risk management, data management and innovation management.

Contact us!

Contact us for more information on the project

[GET IN TOUCH](#)

Figure 20: View of “About VitiGEOSS page”

2.2.2 Pilots

The solution of VitiGEOSS will be validated in **three vineyards** in Spain, Italy and Portugal from Symington, Mastroberardino and Miguel Torres wineries. The vineyards from the end users will be used for the calibration of the VitiGEOSS services [LINK TO SOLUTION PAGE] and tested to be able to correct the models in future versions.

Portugal

This demonstration site is part of [Symington Family Estates](#) vineyards, one of the principal Port Wine and Douro wine producers and leading vineyard owner in the Douro Valley. Located in Douro Superior region, the vineyard testing VitiGEOSS solution has a total of 85 ha vineyards.

Italy

This demonstration site is owned by [Mastroberardino Società Agricola srl](#), an Italian winery located in the Campania region. The family owns an extensive network of vineyards in Italy, including a vineyard in Mirabella Eclano Estate, in the heart of the Taurasi DOC area which will serve VitiGEOSS as a validation scenario. The estate covers 65 hectares on hill territory with an altitude between 350 and 450 meters above sea level.

Spain

[Torres](#), a family winery with vineyards in Spain, Chile and California, is the third end-user that will be validating VitiGEOSS solution. The demonstration site is located in Aranyó estate, in the area of Juneda (Lleida). It belongs to Torres since the end of the nineties and presents a typically continental climate about 400 meters above sea level.

The agriculture sector in Europe

The European Union is the **world's biggest wine producer** and winemaking is the main economic activity of many regions in the South of Europe.

Therefore, the wine sector **invests heavily in state-of-the-art technology in order to develop innovative solutions for maintaining quality and sustainability requirements.**

HIGHLIGHTED DATA: 20% of CO₂ emissions come from agricultural activities, 60% of the world wine is produced in the EU, 20% of the total employment in EU agriculture comes from the winery sector, 3M employees in the wine sector in the EU

Sustainable agriculture

Agriculture plays an important role in climate change effects itself, being responsible for **more than 20% of CO₂ emissions**. Sustainable agriculture has the purpose to **maximise the net benefit for people by developing new farming practices and methodologies** to meet current and future societal needs for food, ecosystem services and human health, whilst reducing the climate change negative effects.

According to [some studies](#), the shifting patterns of agricultural production in response to climate change could cause a decrease between 25%-75% of major wine producing regions by 2050. This will have catastrophic direct effects from economic, social and cultural points of view.

A better prediction of the main grapevine phenological stages and being able to optimise critical vineyard management practices, will help to improve the wineries resources and tasks planning, and reduce the emissions of greenhouse gases as well as the amount of chemicals and fertilizers used on the fields, thus decreasing negative environmental externalities and climate change effects.

The use of Earth Observation Data in agriculture

Satellite data make possible to extract useful indicators to promote a better management and planning of fields and vineyards, as well as the optimisation of innovative agricultural practices. The richness of remote sensing data is crucial to obtain up-to-date information on farmland and agricultural processes.

The use of open resources such as Earth Observation services can improve the efficiency of vineyards thanks to accurate mapping, novel production indicators, image and time series processing and an accurate and improved forecast.

Pilots

The solution of VitiqeOSS will be validated in **three vineyards** in Spain, Italy and Portugal from Symington, Mastroberardino and Miguel Torres wineries.

The vineyards from the end users will be used for the calibration of the VitiqeOSS services and tested to be able to correct the models in future versions.

Portugal

Quinta do Ataíde

This demonstration site is part of **Symington Family Estates** vineyards, one of the principal Port Wine and Douro wine producers and leading vineyard owner in the Douro Valley. Located in Douro Superior region, the vineyard testing VitiqeOSS solution has a total of 85 ha vineyards.

Italy

Mirabella Eclano Estate

This demonstration site is owned by **Mastroberardino Società Agricola srl**, an Italian winery located in the Campania region. The family owns an extensive network of vineyards in Italy, including a vineyard in Mirabella Eclano Estate, in the heart of the Taurasi DOC area which will serve VitiqeOSS as a validation scenario. The estate covers 65 hectares on hill territory with an altitude between 350 and 450 meters above sea level.

Spain

Juneda

Torres, a family winery with vineyards in Spain, Chile and California, is the third end-user that will be validating VitIGE OSS solution. The demonstration site is located in Aranyó estate, in the area of Juneda (Lleida). It belongs to Torres since the end of the nineties and presents a typically continental climate about 400 meters above sea level.

The agriculture sector in Europe

The European Union is the **world's biggest wine producer** and winemaking is the main economic activity of many regions in the South of Europe.

Therefore, the wine sector **invests heavily in state-of-the-art technology in order to develop innovative solutions for maintaining quality and sustainability requirements.**

Sustainable agriculture

Agriculture plays an important role in climate change effects itself, being responsible for **more than 20% of CO₂ emissions**. Sustainable agriculture has the purpose to **maximise the net benefit for people by developing new farming practices and methodologies** to meet current and future societal needs for food, ecosystem services and human health, whilst reducing the climate change negative effects.

According to **some studies**, the shifting patterns of agricultural production in response to climate change could cause a decrease between 25%-75% of major wine producing regions by 2050. This will have catastrophic direct effects from economic, social and cultural points of view.

A better prediction of the main grapevine phenological stages and being able to optimise critical vineyard management practices, will help to improve the wineries resources and tasks planning, and reduce the emissions of greenhouse gases as well as the amount of chemicals and fertilizers used on the fields, thus decreasing negative environmental externalities and climate change effects.

20%

CO₂ emissions come from agricultural activities

20%

of the total employment in EU agriculture comes from the winery sector

60%

of the world wine is produced in the EU

3M

employees in the EU wine sector

The use of Earth Observation data in agriculture

Satellite data make possible to extract useful indicators to promote a better management and planning of fields and vineyards, as well as the optimisation of innovative agricultural practices. The richness of remote sensing data is crucial to obtain up-to-date information on farmland and agricultural processes.

The use of open resources such as Earth Observation services can improve the efficiency of vineyards thanks to accurate mapping, novel production indicators, image and time series processing and an accurate and improved forecast.

Figure 21: View of pilots' page

2.2.3 Partners

Section devoted to the partners' corporate information. This page includes a first section with a brief description of the consortium, followed by a portfolio with the logos of the different partners, leading to a specific page per partners with their contact details.

VitiGEOSS project gathers a multidisciplinary team comprising 9 partners from 4 European countries providing the necessary range of expertise, competence and operational capacity to deliver the innovative project objectives.

4 research centres, 2 technological companies and 3 wine producers.

Eurecat

eurecat Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The centre offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

With a vast experience in the application of new technologies to the development of early warning systems and decision support system for reducing environmental impacts, Eurecat is in charge of coordinating the project and leading the tasks related to the application of semantic technology and big data analytics to provide a semantic data broker that permit to generate newer participatory services. We are also responsible for carrying out environmental and safety impact analyses, implement strategies to obtain a final marketable product, managing IPR and the project's communication and dissemination activities.

www.eurecat.org

Twitter: @Eurecat_News

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/Eurecatorg/>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company-beta/9355193/>

Youtube https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCWeVIFJ__t_6ozc7bDaKZw

Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

**Barcelona
Supercomputing
Center**
Centro Nacional de Supercomputación

BSC is the leading supercomputing center in Spain. It specialises in high-performance computing. It has a dual role: providing infrastructure and a supercomputing service for Spanish and European scientists and generating

knowledge and technology to be transferred to society.

It has a staff of about 700 workers, most of whom are scientists who use supercomputers to conduct research in Computer Science, Life Sciences, Earth Sciences, and Engineering. The BSC is at the service of the international scientific community through the European research

infrastructure PRACE (Partnership for Advanced Computing in Europe) and manages the Spanish Supercomputing Network (RES).

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

BSC is leading the project's communication and dissemination and a task in the WP on intelligent services for vineyard management, consisting in developing weather and climate forecasts. We are also contributing to the task of disease and forecast management system.

www.bsc.es

Twitter: https://twitter.com/BSC_CNS

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/BSCCNS>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/barcelona-supercomputing-center/>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/BSCCNS>

Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/bsc_cns/

eLEAF

eLEAF is a Dutch high-tech company that provides satellite-based applications and data to optimize agricultural production, water resources management and agricultural index insurance.

eLEAF is the developer and owner of a set of algorithms that transform meteorological and remote sensing-based data into quantitative crop, water and climate parameters per pixel.

eLEAF's agricultural products include our crop monitoring platform FieldLook, which provides end-users with actionable information on crop's health and water use. In the Western Cape of South Africa our FruitLook service, an instantiation of FieldLook, supports wine grape and other fruit farmers to enhance on-farm resources and crop management.

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

eLEAF is leading the WP on the Integrated Vineyard Management Application Portal and tasks on key crop indicators tracking, data service management and operational provision of the services output data.

www.eleaf.com

Twitter: @eleaf

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/eleaf/>

Familia Torres

Familia Torres is one of Spain's most renowned family-owned winery, led by the fifth generation who is focusing on single-vineyard wines and the recovery of ancestral varieties to face climate change.

Founded in 1870, Familia Torres has been historically linked to the Catalan regions of Penedès, Conca de Barberà, Priorat and Costers del Segre, but has also extended its presence to vineyards and wineries in preeminent Spanish

wine regions, as well as Chile and California. Strongly committed to the environment and sustainability, it is a member of the Primum Familiae Vini, an association of 12 wine families who are among the most prestigious wine producers in Europe.

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

Familia Torres will provide data to co-design the intelligent services and will do the maintenance and monitoring of the trial plots for testing and refining of the platform. Familia Torres will also validate that VITIGE OSS cloud-based application portal delivers against the user requirements. On the other hand, the company will participate in tasks related to Knowledge transfer and added value provision to target groups, and as hosts of a local session addressed to local farmers and rural communities with the aim to educate on sustainable agricultural practices to improve productivity.

www.torres.es

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/familiatorres> and <https://twitter.com/TorresWines>

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/familiatorresoficial>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/familiatorres/>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/c/FamiliaTorres>

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/familiatorres1870/>

Price Waterhouse Coopers - PwC

PwC firms help organizations and individuals create the value they're looking for. We're a network of firms in 155 countries with more than 284,000 people who are committed to delivering quality in assurance, tax and advisory services.

PwC in Portugal, Angola and Cape Verde together has 1.636 staff, including 42 partners, of which 26 are in Lisbon, 11 in Oporto and 5 in Luanda.

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

PwC will be present throughout all phases of the project, providing support to all the members. PwC will have major responsibility for the phase: Commercial Innovation and Market Penetration. The Commercial Innovation and Market Penetration phase will support research and commercial exploitation of the project results on an international scale and the preparation of a realistic exploitation strategy and business plan. Specific objectives:

- Define a successful market entry strategy
- Creation of a financial model and revenue estimation for the partners

www.pwc.pt

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/pwcportugal>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/pwc-portugal>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCDzIsrcIC4rZcss5aTWQuWQ>

Instagram: https://www.instagram.com/pwc_portugal/

Symington Family Estates

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

www.symington.com

Twitter <https://twitter.com/SymingtonFamily>

Instagram <https://www.instagram.com/symingtonfamilyestates/>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UChbyKC8sMFx430aylL2TQWg>

Fondazione LINKS

LINKS aims to be the Italian reference point to give value to the intellectual property developed by academic research, to accelerate the technology transfer and to support the companies to boost their business.

Our mission is to promote the interaction between the ecosystem made by research, start-ups, enterprises, Public Administrations and citizens. We enhance the innovation process also providing professional and financial support. We are the ones to call if you need to protect, to exploit and to bring into the market your intellectual property. We start in Turin, but we challenge the world.

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

LINKS is responsible for the task that aims to establish a service able to monitor the lifecycle of the winegrapes throughout the entire season by coupling the outputs of phenological prediction models (provided by UNAP), satellite and in-field observations acquired through both fixed cameras and drones. Claudio Rossi from LINKS is also the technical and quality manager of the project.

www.linksfoundation.com/

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/linksfoundation/>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/linksfoundation/>

Youtube <https://twitter.com/LinksFoundation/>

Instagram: <https://www.youtube.com/channel/UC3fBPkCm1UzB-0A3sdzagxA>

Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II

The University of Naples Federico II (UNINA) is one of the oldest Italian University and was founded in 1224 by Frederick II, King of Sicily and Holy Roman Emperor. Nowadays, it is the biggest University in southern Italy.

The technical contribution of UNINA to the Project will be made by the Department of Agricultural Sciences that is settled at the historical Faculty of Agriculture in Portici (Napoli) and is a long-

established Institution with expertise in all the fields of plant and food sciences, including horticulture, genetics, environmental physiology and ecology. The Departmental Division of Grape and Wine Sciences focuses on the study of all the aspects related to Viticulture and Enology.

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

UNINA will carry out cultivar-specific calibrations of the phenological models (WP2), and design and manage, throughout the project, the pilot plots at the demo-sites in order to provide the datasets required for the fine-tuning of the calibration of all the models included in VITIGE OSS (the phenological stage prediction models, the key crop indicators tracking models, the downscaled weather forecast models, and the vine disease early warning system forecast) and for the validation of the VITIGE OSS services (WP4). UNINA will lead WP4 - Demonstration.

www.unina.it

Twitter <https://twitter.com/uninait>

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/unina.it>

LinkedIn <https://www.linkedin.com/company/university-of-naples-federico-ii/?originalSubdomain=es>

Youtube <https://www.youtube.com/user/uninavideonews>

Instagram <https://www.instagram.com/uninait/>

Mastroberardino Società Agricola srl

Mastroberardino Società Agricola srl is one of Italy's most renowned family-owned winery, led by the tenth generation who is focusing on indigenous grape varieties.

Mastroberardino company is fully committed to traditional cultivation of ancient grape varieties, with ability to blend modern technology with time-tested techniques. The Mastroberardino long term goal has been focusing on wines reflecting the typical characters and notes of the Irpinia territory (located in the province of Avellino - Campania region - Italy). The family owns an extensive network of vineyards in the DOCG's areas located in different altitudes, starting from 350 meters above the sea level up to 600 meters. The benefit is the high difference in temperature between daytime and night, a unique microclimate in the viticulture scenario.

Contribution to VitiGEOSS

The Mastroberardino role is to support the research in several vineyards planted in different terroirs with the aim to achieve the calibration of phenological and management models. The

company will provide data to WP2 to co-design the intelligent services and in WP4 to manage the trial plots.

www.mastroberardino.com

Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/MastroberardinoVineyards>

Youtube https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCdMVN_1iwZwTQlqxjwmzIPA

Instagram: <https://www.instagram.com/mastroberardinowinery/>

Partners

Home / Partners

Partners

VitIGE OSS project gathers a multidisciplinary team comprising 9 partners from 4 European countries providing the necessary range of expertise, competence and operational capacity to deliver the innovative project objectives.

<p>Symington Family Estates</p>	<p>PwC</p>	<p>UNINA</p>
<p>BSC</p>	<p>eLEAF</p>	<p>Mastroberardino Società Agricola srl</p>
<p>Familia Torres</p>	<p>Links</p>	<p>Eurecat</p>

Figure 22: View of partners' page

eurecat

Eurecat is the leading Technology Centre of Catalonia, providing the industrial and business sector with differential technology and advanced expertise.

The centre offers solutions to their innovation needs and boosts their competitiveness in a fast-paced environment. It brings together the expertise of 650 professionals who generate a volume of income of 50M€ per year. Serving more than a thousand companies, Eurecat is involved in 200 projects of R&D national and international with high strategic value.

Contribution to VITIGE OSS

With a vast experience in the application of new technologies to the development of early warning systems and decision support systems for reducing environmental impacts, Eurecat is in charge of coordinating the project and leading the tasks related to the application of semantic technology and big data analytics to provide a semantic data broker that permit to generate newer participatory services. We are also responsible for carrying out environmental and safety impact analyses, implement strategies to obtain a final marketable product, managing IPR and the project's communication and dissemination activities.

www.eurecat.org/en

Figure 23: View of partners' information page

2.2.4 Deliverables

This page will include a list of all deliverables to be prepared during the project and will provide access to the executive summary of confidential ones and full access to the public ones.

Deliverables

Home / Deliverables

Recent Tweets

VITIGE OSS Retweeted

INEA @inea_eu

Did you know that #MachineLearning & High Performance Computing #HPC can be used to prevent & control #grape vine diseases?

Check out how the #CEFTelecom project @grapevine_pro is doing it resulting in higher quality & safer products

grapevine-project.eu #EU #OpenData

4h

VITIGE OSS @vitigeoss_EU

Follow the the #sustainablewine virtual conference and learn more about the future of wine and how the #wine industry can respond to #sustainability pressures and create business opportunities

@martaterrado from @BSC_CNS

Register here futurewineforum.com

Deliverables

WP1 – Project Management

- >> D1.1 – Data Management Plan – Initial report
- >> D1.2 – Data Management Plan – (update) M18
- >> D1.3 – Data Management Plan – (update) M36
- >> D1.4 – Data Management Plan – Final report
- >> D1.5 – First Yearly progress reports
- >> D1.6 – Second Yearly Progress Report
- >> D1.7 – Third Yearly Progress Report
- >> D1.8 – Final – Innovation Management outcomes analysis
- >> D1.9 – First Innovation Management outcomes analysis

WP2 – Intelligent (information) services on vineyard management

- >> D2.1 – Intelligent services requirements
- >> D2.2 – Design of Intelligent services and data repositories
- >> D2.3 – Intelligent services and data repositories evaluation and release notes
- >> D2.4 – Testing methodology and results
- >> D2.5 – Testing methodology and results (update)

WP3 – Integrated Vineyard Management Application Portal (DSS)

- >> D3.1 – Report on use case scenarios descriptions
- >> D3.2 – Deployment of the VitiGEOSS cloud-based application portal
- >> D3.3 – Initial Report on services configuration
- >> D3.4 – Final Report on services configuration
- >> D3.5 – Report on authorisations with hyperledger results
- >> D3.6 – Report on operational application portal testing – Initial
- >> D3.7 – Initial Report on statistics and evolution of VitiGEOSS platform
- >> D3.8 – Final Report on statistics and evolution of VitiGEOSS platform
- >> D3.9 – System architecture blueprint
- >> D3.10 – Report on operational application portal testing – Final

Figure 24: View of deliverables page

2.3 Platform

VitiGEOSS platform

VitiGEOSS will use free-of-charge satellite imagery and EO products from the European [Copernicus Programme](#) and [NASA](#) coupling them with in-field and near in-field data to extract useful indicators for a better management of vineyards and the optimisation of agricultural practices.

This solution will provide support to growers and will be a single access point for wine producers that aims to be sustainable and support a circular economy approach.

VitiGEOSS solution will be deployed as a cloud-based Applications Portal co-designed with end-users. The platform infrastructure will include an API Service Store for service providers and, from another hand, the Application Dashboard for wine producers.

The solution developed will be the first application offering integrated services for sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions, crop management, disease warnings, business operations and sustainability monitoring.

Information services

Weather and climate forecast

Advanced techniques to apply sub-seasonal (for the next weeks, up to 1 month) to seasonal climate forecasts (for the next months) in combination with short term weather forecasts (up to 10 days) to help farmers **prepare in advance for unusual climate conditions and extreme events that can damage the crop.**

Phenological monitoring

Automated system to predict and monitor the whole phenological annual cycle through the synergic use of phenological models, satellite and in-field observations to **better plan and organise the whole vineyard management and optimise resources.**

Crop status

Satellite imagery to monitor key indicators describing vegetation health status, crop productivity, crop water consumption and crop nitrogen content to **optimise irrigation, sampling or selective harvesting leading to better grape quality and production.**

Disease management

Tool for forecasting the disease evolution taking into account the meteorological conditions and crop status to optimise the number of treatments and resources used to assure its effectivity.

Business and sustainability manager

Resource optimiser and planner service capable to plan best timing for field operations, better planning of resources needed, reduce the use of raw materials and promote a sustainable winegrowing.

Benefits

- Move from stand-alone observations (satellite, in-field) to downstream information services.
- Support farmers by providing early warning and give them the tools to make better decisions in crop management.
- Help farmers to tackle crop problems or affectations using less chemicals and changing their production methods to minimise the pesticide use.
- Results achieved and lessons learned will be used for building capacity on sustainability among agricultural communities, to benefit local economies, strengthen skills, competences and abilities to advance the development of services based on the use of Earth observation systems.

info@vitigeoss.eu

VITIGE OSS

Search...

HOME ABOUT VITIGE OSS PLATFORM NEWS & EVENTS CONTACT

VitiGE OSS platform

Home / VitiGE OSS platform

VitiGE OSS platform

VitiGE OSS will use free-of-charge satellite imagery and EO products from the European Copernicus Programme and NASA coupling them with in-field and near in-field data to extract useful indicators for a better management of vineyards and the optimisation of agricultural practices.

This solution will provide support to growers and will be a single access point for wine producers that aim to be sustainable and support a circular economy approach.

VitiGE OSS solution will be deployed as a cloud-based Applications Portal co-designed with end-users. The platform infrastructure will include an API Service Store for service providers and, from another hand, the Application Dashboard for wine producers.

The solution developed will be the first application offering integrated services for sub-seasonal and seasonal predictions, crop management, disease warnings, business operations and sustainability monitoring

Information services

- + Weather and climate forecast
- + Phenological monitoring
- + Crop status
- + Disease management
- + Business and sustainability manager

Figure 25: View of “VitiGEOSS platform” page

2.4 News & Events

News

This page will show articles on VitiGEOSS project advances and results, as well as general assembly meetings or articles written by partners on project topics.

Upcoming events

This page will include an agenda announcing events where VitiGEOSS consortium is attending or participating (conferences, meetings, fairs, congresses and workshops) and a list of articles regarding the events attended, type of dissemination activity, target-profile/audience covered, number of attendees and an overview of the feedback received.

Within this page VitiGEOSS events such as the final conference, technical webinars and participatory workshops will be announced and promoted. Each event will count with a specific page with the information on the event, agenda and form to register. After the event, the presentations and documents delivered during the event will be made available for download through the page, as well as video recording of the sessions.

Media

Section created to include the project’s press releases and key media coverage on the project.

News & Events

Home / News & Events

Latest news

18
11, 2020

VitiGEOSS project kicks-off!

The VitiGEOSS project has kicked off on September 2020 with the objective to develop a vineyard innovative tool based on the integration of Earth Observation services and in-field sensors to increase resolution and reliability of satellite information applied to viticulture.

Past events

VitiGEOSS takes part in the e-shape project general assembly
October 19 - October 21

VitiGEOSS project coordinator María Navarro from Eurecat Technology Center has presented the project at the e-shape project General Assembly celebrated in an online format between 19th – 21st October.

Eurecat brings VitiGEOSS at the "Fira de Novembre" online event
November 6 - November 15

The VitiGEOSS project has been presented during the "Fira de Novembre de Vilanova i la Geltrú" online event which took place from 6th – 15th of November.

Figure 26: View of "VitiGEOSS news & events" page

2.5 Dissemination

Promotional materials

Page giving access to all project promotional materials produced (rollups, posters, infosheets, etc.).

Scientific publications

Page giving access to all scientific publications related to the project's research in open access journals or as conference proceedings.

Audiovisual materials

A page to allocate all VitiGEOSS audiovisual materials will be created. In this page, users will be able to view the project's demo video to guide users through the different smart services developed and testimonial videos of end-users. Other videos produced by partners illustrating the project work will be gathered and published in this page.

Capacity building resources

Page making available resources related to the capacity building task or other tasks of the project.

2.6 Contact

This section shows a form for visitors to send comments and questions. The form includes the fields (Name, Surname, Email, Company, Phone, Subject and Message).

On the other hand, the email info@vitigeoss.eu has been created and is shown at the website as another way of contact. The project coordinator has access to that email in order to manage all information requests received.

Figure 27: View of VitiGEOSS contact page

3. Layout

The VitiGEOSS website’s menu is available from all pages, allowing visitors to find the information that they are interested in no matter how they reached the sight.

The overall design and home page of the website includes the following elements:

Header

- VitiGEOSS logo to appear in the header.
- Navigation menu.
- Search button.
- Acces to Social Media platforms (Twitter, YouTube - when created).

Footer

- EU logo to appear in the footer. Under the logo will appear the phrase *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 869565. This website reflects only the author’s view and the European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains”.*
- Link to legal notice.
- Link to privacy statement.
- Link to cookies policy.
- Link to newsletter subscription
- Contact info

Figure 28: VitiGEOSS header and footer layout

4. Managing and updating policy

The website has been developed by Eurecat with the inputs received from all partners in the consortium.

The website will be updated from now on by the Communication Leader Eurecat together with the inputs sent by all partners every time a new dissemination action is done, a result is achieved or there are other news worth publishing.

5. Analytics

The VitiGEOSS website has installed **Matomo** in the platform’s back end to monitoring all the traffic and obtain, periodically, reports about the site’s performance. Instead of Google Analytics, Matomo does not compromise data security and privacy, guaranteeing full data ownership and that none of it is ever sent to other services or third parties.

Figure 29: Matomo panel

6. Site hosting, installation & maintenance

Eurecat has been responsible for setting up the website (domain purchase, hosting and Wordpress.org configuration), as well as creating content and design the fixed sections.

As the Communication leader, Eurecat will be responsible for maintaining the site until the project's end and until two years after and adding content to the website. All pages will be optimised for the search engines (SEO), ensuring that VitiGEOSS website is well positioned in the browsers.

7. Data protection

VitiGEOSS website is compliant with all European requirements and standards with regards to data protection and observes the GDPR. *See the legal warning, cookies policy and privacy policy on Annex.*

The website has been adapted to the latest directives published by the Spanish Data Protection Agency (AEPD) on July 2020, which came into force on October 31st 2020 with the purpose to align the cookies installation with the GDPR consent requirements. The latest version of the AEPD "Guidelines on the Use of Cookies", compared with the previous one, specifies that the consent must be granted by clearly accepting the cookies or carrying out similar actions to click "I accept". In that sense, browsing the website or the use the scroll bar cannot be construed as an affirmative action, nor the use of cookie walls that do not provide an alternative to the consent.

In order to comply with the new AEPD directives, EUT, as the owner of the website www.vitigeoss.eu, has installed a cookies banner allowing the user to decide on which non-necessary cookies to install. By complying with the novel regulation, web analytics will only be

tracked for users accepting this type of cookies, which may result in losing some statistics on the number of web visits, page viewed or number of users.

8. Website KPIs

The following table introduces an initial set of VitiGEOSS Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for assessing the website performance. Progress until the end of the project will be reported in the interim progress reports.

As we expect to not be able to record all website analytics due to the new AEPD regulation on third-party cookies, such the ones used for getting analytics on website performance (see *more information on section 7. Data Protection*), KPIs related to the website activity have been designed and established with caution taking the regulation into account.

Strategy	Indicator	Means of verification	Target by the end of the project
Website	Number of web visits	Matomo Analytics	>3.500
	Number Pages Viewed		>10.000
	Number page / session		>1.0
	Number users		>1.500
	Avg. session time		>1.00 min

Table 1: VitiGEOSS website KPIs

Annex

1. Legal warning

In compliance with Law 34/2002 of 11 July on Information Society and Electronic Commerce Services, the User is informed that the owner of the website www.vitigeoss.eu FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, whose identification information is as follows:

Registered office: Av. Universitat Autònoma, 23

Post code: 08290

Town/City: Cerdanyola del Vallès

Province: Barcelona

CIF: G66210345

E-mail: info@eurecat.org

Registry data: Registered in the Foundations Registry of the Generalitat de Catalunya with the number 2826.

ACCESS TO THE WEBSITE

This legal notice regulates the access and use of the website by Users and aims to inform about the services and products of the entity and allow general access for all Internet users.

Any person who accesses or uses the Website is considered a User and accepts, without reservations of any kind, each and every one of these general conditions, as well as of other special conditions that, if applicable, govern the use of the Portal or the services linked to it.

The User must carefully read the Legal Notice and the Privacy and Cookies Policies when they intend to use the Website, since FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to make, at any time and without prior notice, any modification or update of the contents and services, of the present provisions for access and use and, in general, of all the elements that comprise the design and configuration of its Website. If you do not accept the conditions of access and use, please refrain from using the Website and its content.

USE OF THE WEBSITE

The User undertakes to make diligent use of the Website, as well as the information relating to its services and/or activities, in full compliance with the applicable regulations, ethics and generally accepted good practices and law and order, the conditions of access and use and any other conditions established on the Website.

In addition, the user agrees to refrain from using any of the content for illegal purposes or effects, prohibited in this document, which may be harmful to the rights and interests of third parties, or that in any way may damage, disable, overload, deteriorate or prevent the normal use of the content (hardware and software) of other Users or of any Internet user in general.

OPERATION OF THE WEBSITE

In the event of non-compliance with the conditions of the Legal Notice, or the Privacy and Cookies Policies, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT reserves the right to limit, suspend and/or exclude access to its website, adopting any technical measure necessary in this respect. FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will do everything possible to keep the website in good working order, preventing faults, or repairing them and keeping the contents up to date. However, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT does not guarantee the availability and continuity of access to the Website or the absence of errors in the content.

LIABILITY

The User is solely liable for the use that they may make of any information or mechanism of the Website.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will not be liable for any damage to the hardware and/or software of the User that may arise from access and use of the Website. Likewise, it will be not liable for damages or losses that may be caused by accessing and/or using the information on the Website, and specifically those that may occur in computer systems or those caused by computer viruses/attacks, crashes, interruptions, absence or defects in connectivity and/or the Internet.

The User will be liable for the damages and/or losses that FUNDACIÓ EURECAT may suffer as a result of the breach of any of the obligations to which they are subject to through this Legal Notice, applicable regulations and the Privacy and Cookies Policies.

POLICY ON LINKS

a) Web linking:

Third parties who intend to include a link on this website must comply with current legislation and may not host content that is inappropriate, illegal, pornographic, violent, etc.

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT will in no case be liable for the content of that Website, nor promote, guarantee, supervise or recommend the content therein.

If the linking Website fails to comply with any of the above aspects, it will be obliged to delete the link immediately.

b) Linking website:

This Website may include links to third-party websites that allow the User to access them. Nonetheless, FUNDACIÓ EURECAT is not liable for the content of these linked websites, but rather the User will be responsible for accepting and verifying access each time they connect.

These links or mentions have a use that does not imply the support, approval, commercialization or any relationship of this website and the persons or entities that own the site where they are located.

INTELLECTUAL AND INDUSTRIAL PROPERTY RIGHTS OF THE CONTENT

FUNDACIÓ EURECAT, or its licensors, are holders of all intellectual property rights over the Contents of the Website, understood as all the designs, databases, underlying computer programs (source code, included), as well as the different elements that make up the Website (texts, graphics, photographs, videos, colours, etc.), structure, layout, etc. The trademarks and trade names ("distinctive signs") are owned by FUNDACIÓ EURECAT or the licensors.

The use of the Website by the User does not imply the transfer of any intellectual or industrial property rights. The User is totally prohibited from reproducing, copying, distributing, making available or publicly communicating, transforming or modifying the Contents or Distinctive Signs in any way, unless the authorization of the owner of the corresponding rights is granted or it is legally permitted.

APPLICABLE LEGISLATION

The Legal Notice will be governed and interpreted in accordance with Spanish legislation.

Any conflict that may arise from accessing the website will be submitted to the relevant courts or tribunals for resolution in accordance with consumer and user regulations.

CONTACT

For any questions or comments on this Legal Notice you can contact us at legal@eurecat.org.

2. Cookies policy

WHAT ARE COOKIES AND WHY DO WE USE THEM ON THE WEBSITE?

A cookie is a file that is downloaded to the user's device when they access certain websites which stores and retrieves information about the browsing activity on their computer.

Cookies allow this website, among other things, to store and retrieve information about the user's decisions and habits. The cookies that exist on this website are necessary for it to function.

It is important to highlight that the use of cookies does not provide access to the user's personal data.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES EXIST?

Depending on the time they remain active, Cookies can be divided into session or persistent cookies.

- **Session cookies** are designed to collect and store data while the user accesses a website and are removed as soon the explorer is closed. They are normally used to store information which only needs to be kept in order to provide the service requested by the user on just one occasion.
- **Persistent cookies** remain stored on the device and can be accessed and handled during a period specified by the user of the cookie, which may be from a few minutes to several years.

Additionally, depending on the organisation managing them, cookies may be classified as first-party or third-party cookies.

- **First-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain managed by the website publisher and are used to provide the service requested by the user.
- **Third-party cookies** are sent to the user's device from a computer or domain that is not managed by the website publisher, but by another organisation that handles data obtained from the cookies.

In terms of their purpose, the types of cookies are:

- **Technical cookies:** Technical cookies allow the user to browse a website, platform or application and use the different service options found there.
- **Profiling cookies:** Profiling cookies allow the user to access the service with some predefined general features based on a series of criteria on the user's device such as language, settings, etc.
- **Analytical cookies:** Analytical cookies allow the website owner to track and analyse user behaviour on the websites to which they are linked. The information collected is used to measure activity on the websites and to create users' browsing profiles, with the aim of introducing improvements.
- **Advertising cookies:** Advertising cookies allow the advertising spaces which the publisher puts on the website to be managed as efficiently as possible.

WHAT TYPE OF COOKIES DOES THE WEBSITE USE?

The user may be consult and set up the website cookies managed by the website publisher at Cookie settings.

The user should take account that although the cookies may be set up, certain cookies are needed and must be installed to ensure the proper access and use of the website, these cookies does not require the user’s agreed neither its management.

COOKIE	TYPE	DURATION	DESCRIPTION
_pk_id.11.cfba	0	1 year	This cookie is installed by Matomo. The cookie is used to calculate visitor, session, camapign data and keep track of site usage for the site's analytics report. The cookies store information anonymously and assigns a randoly generated number to identify unique visitors.
_pk_ses.11.cfba	0	30 min	This cookie is installed by Matomo. The cookie is used to calculate visitor, session, camapign data and keep track of site usage for the site's analytics report. The cookies store information anonymously and assigns a randoly generated number to identify unique visitors.
cookielawinfo-checkbox-necessary	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Necessary".
cookielawinfo-checkbox-non-necessary	0	11 months	This cookie is set by GDPR Cookie Consent plugin. The cookies is used to store the user consent for the cookies in the category "Non Necessary".
test_cookie	0	11 months	Test for GDPR plugin
viewed_cookie_policy	0	11 months	The cookie is set by the GDPR Cookie Consent plugin and is used to store whether or not user has consented to the use of cookies. It does not store any personal data.

HOW DO YOU DISABLE COOKIES IN A BROWSER?

The user can adjust the settings in their browser so as not to accept the use of cookies, in which case the user would not have a customized browsing experience. Choosing this setting may result in certain parts of the website not being accessible, as this may cause less effective browsing.

Most browsers currently allow the user to choose whether they want to accept cookies and which types. These settings are usually found in the “settings” or “preferences” in your browser’s menu.

Depending of the browser used by the user and its functionalities used may suppose the installation of cookies that are considered ad a Third-party cookies. For example, if the user chooses Google’s browser and use its option of translate full website, Google install cookies in the user’s computers that are not managed by the website publisher. The settings of the browser cookies should be done by the user directly at the browser website.

These are the instructions to change the cookie settings in the main browsers:

- [Information about cookies for Internet Explorer.](#)
- [Information about cookies for Mozilla Firefox.](#)

- [Information about cookies for Opera.](#)
- [Information about cookies for Google Chrome.](#)
- [Information about cookies for Safari.](#)

3. Privacy policy

WHO IS THE DATA CONTROLLER FOR YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

Data controller: FUNDACIÓ EURECAT (“EURECAT”)

Tax ID number: G66210345

Address: Parc Tecnològic del Vallès. Avinguda Universitat Autònoma, 23 08290 Cerdanyola del Vallès

Email address: legal@eurecat.org

Telephone: +34 93 238 14 00

Data protection delegate contact: dpo@eurecat.org

FOR WHAT PURPOSE WILL BE PROCESSED YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

Your personal data received through the contact form will be processed for the purpose of managing your query or request. However, the data collected as the result of the cookies installation, will be used for collecting statistical information on the browsing of users and improve the website based on their browsing habits. You may consult further information about the cookies purposes and its data treatment at the Cookies Policy

On our website, there may be several forms that collects your personal data for specific purposes. In those cases, you will be previously informed about the specific data treatment information to each case, and your specific consent shall be sought.

IS IT MANDATORY TO PROVIDE ALL THE INFORMATION REQUESTED IN THE FORMS ON THE WEBSITE?

The user must complete the fields marked as “required”. Failure to complete the required personal information or to partially do so may mean that Fundació Eurecat cannot meet your requests and, consequently, Fundació Eurecat will be exempt from any liability for the non-provision or incomplete provision of the requested services.

The personal data provided by the User to Fundació Eurecat must be up to date so that the information in our records is current and without errors. The user will be liable for the veracity of the data provided.

HOW LONG WILL YOUR PERSONAL DATA BE RETAINED FOR?

The personal data obtained, will be kept for the duration of the purposes for which it was collected for and its erasure is not requested, and consent is not revoked. The personal data, also, will be kept, in any case, during the legal term applicable.

WHAT IS THE LAWFUL BASIS FOR US TO PROCESS YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

The lawful basis for the processing of your data is the consent provided through acceptance of the data processing clause.

WHAT RECIPIENTS WILL YOUR DATA BE SHARED WITH?

The Personal data received through the forms of the website may be shared with members of the project for the exclusive purpose of managing your query or request and be able to send you the latest news about the project through periodic newsletters. You may consult the list of members here.

The personal data may be shared to third-parties whose develop services to the Data Controller, those ones who has access to the personal data will not treat the personal data fort their own or different purposes and they will not sold or rent them.

The personal data will not be passed on to any other third-parties, unless there is a legal obligation to do so.

WHAT ARE YOUR RIGHTS REGARDING YOUR PERSONAL DATA?

The user may exercise their right to access their personal data, to request the rectification of inaccurate data and, where applicable, to request the data to be erased if it is no longer necessary for the purposes for which it was collected. The user may also exercise their right to data portability and to the restriction of or opposition to the processing of their data, in certain circumstances and for reasons related to their specific situation.

The user also has the right to revoke their consent at any time, without any retroactive effect on the processing of their personal data carried out until that point.

The user may exercise the aforementioned rights, under the terms provided for in current legislation, at the registered office of Fundació Eurecat or request to do so by sending an email to legal@eurecat.org .

Should the user not receive a satisfactory response and should they wish to make a complaint or obtain more information on any of these rights, they may contact the Spanish Data Protection Agency (www.agpd.es - C/ Jorge Juan, 6, Madrid).

AUTOMATED DECISIONS

The personal data shall not be submitted to automated decisions.

The personal data may be processed to create profiles according to the cookies that has been consented to installed by the user.

INTERNATIONAL DATA TRANSFERS

The personal data shall not be summitted to international transfers out of the European Union. However, the Data Controller may have several suppliers that develop services out of the UE, in those cases, Fundació Eurecat shall assure that the personal data shall be treat with the legal requirements through agreement that may include standard contractual clauses or privacy certification.

WHAT SECURITY MEASURES HAS THE INSTITUTION IMPLEMENTED?

Fundació Eurecat declares that it has implemented the necessary technical and organisational security measures that guarantee the security of the User's personal data and avoid its alteration, loss, processing and/or unauthorised access considering the state of technology, the nature of the stored data and the risks to which it is exposed, whether from human action or from the physical or natural environment, in accordance with the provisions of current regulations.

SOCIAL MEDIA

VitiGEOSS, a project coordinated by Fundació Eurecat has a profile on Twitter for publishing and disseminating information about the services provided through the website, interacting with users and acting as a customer service and social interaction channel.

The following are links to the privacy policies of the social networks on which VitiGEOSS has an active profile:

Twitter: <https://twitter.com/en/privacy>